
Vegetative Reproduction and Root System Development analysis towards flowering and maturation of defined crops in Ghana with Cassava as the focused Crop.

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ABSTRACT

Our survival on planet earth is highly dependent on food and water. Man cannot feed on air and neither drink air for his/her entire life on earth but resort to eating food and drinking water for energy generation in order to achieve daily working demands. Food production and planting using standard procedures hence becomes a necessity to achieve this aim. Crops such as cassava is planted to develop roots, develops leaves, access all the conditions necessary for photosynthesis, grow gradually to flowering stage and finally mature. With this, cassava is obtained to be processed into all kinds of cassava food products like for banku, Gari, fufu, ampesi etc. This has gone on for generation but the current cassava on the market is facing the challenges of being not in good condition all year round to meet food demands in Ghana. During the course of the year, most of the cassava's are very bad hence unable to meet food demands such as for fufu and ampesi. This is usually the case during a changeover of seasons (from dry season to rainy season). This research work therefore sort to investigate the vegetative reproduction of cassava and analyze the root system development towards flowering and maturity. It will also examine how to obtain good quality sweet consumable cassava that can be used all year round in Ghana to meet various food demands. Research findings indicated that all kinds of cassava varieties exists in Ghana based on purpose and what it's intended for. Stem cutting is used vegetatively each season for cassava multiplication and production of cassava tubers. The good sweet quality cassava variety (for ampesi) enjoyed in the 1980s and 1990s exist but to a percentage of 20% in the study area. This good sweet soft edible cassava variety (Tekbankye) needs to be worked on, its sticks multiplied for mass production of cassava tubers since it's comparable to yam. Since its comparable to yam and can be eaten with good stews, its mass production should be propagated. Why comparable to yam is because they all give carbohydrates if possible same calories of energy.

Keywords: Cassava, Vegetative reproduction, roots, maturation, Tekbankye, Soil, farmlands, carbohydrates, Fufu, Gari, ampesi.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Vegetative or asexual reproduction method has been used over centuries to replenish crops of the same kind and species to obtain food for man's existence. The existence of mankind on earth is only dependent on all kinds of food and vegetable products in order to obtain a balance diet to support the body. With this in mind food has to be produced in high quantity to boost the Ghanaian economy and exports some to help and feed the world. Ghana is blessed with good fertile lands to support plant and food production. It's only in the northern part of Ghana which has almost all lands degraded of rich nutrients to support plant production. And even that, various crops such as millet, maize and others are planted during the rainy season to support food production in Ghana.

Cassava which is cultivated by vegetative or asexual reproduction using the stem is one of the main food products in Ghana. It can also be cultivated sexually using the seed but most importantly done is using the stem. It is cultivated in all the regions in Ghana to meet yearly food demands. This has been over the years as it's cultivated yearly for the local market. This is processed into food products such as for fufu, Gari, for banku, for starch and raw cooked cassava for food. The raw cassava for normal food is now a problem as most of these produced cassava's are in bad state after harvesting. They are unable to meet normal food eating and fufu producing demand. The poor quality condition of these cassava is always at its peak during the changeover of raining season in Ghana.

The changeover of raining season is basically the shift from dry season to rainy season in Ghana each year. This is a special case in the southern part of Ghana. Cassava production in Ghana especially in the southern part of Ghana is at a high rate in order to meet demands all year round. Even though some varieties of cassava are profoundly meant for Gari production in Ghana, the once to meet demands in the direction of raw cassava for food and fufu are facing the challenges of being of good quality and sweet to meet this demand. The cassava solely meant for Gari, starch and cassava dough production does not pass the test of being of good quality and sweet. Only those meant for raw cassava food and for fufu production needs the assessment for good quality and sweet before being established as eatable cassava. By percentage determination on a given day for cassava for fufu preparation, a ratio of 80% : 20% will be established when compared the unusable cassava : usable cassava ratio. In such a situation, 80% of the bad cassava will be thrown away or disposed off. This reduces the quantity of fufu for the family and waste of time and resources. This is a challenge which requires investigation and stringent action to bring the cassava back to its natural state as was seen in the 1980's.

I believe various investigations and researches have been done into cassava production and how to obtain different varieties for the local and international market. But there is the need to maintain the basis of the staple food. Which is its good quality

and sweetness as this cassava was serving as a staple food for the young and old in Ghana years back. This is not the case today as about 95% people in Ghana do not eat this food anymore due to the loss in quality, freshness and sweetness of the staple food. The current generation and crop of Ghanaians do not see the essence and importance of this staple food as they frown and sees it as food meant for the poor in society. This stable food is comparable to plantain, cocoyam, yam etc but it's only usable in the direction of fufu, starch and for cassava dough in Ghana. This is problematic among current Ghanaians and therefore a requirement and need to protect it as a natural resources in Ghana for now and future generation as it was protected by past and gone generations. Ghana as a country is not technologically inclined as compared to countries like China, Dubai, USA, United Kingdom and other great nations in the world to boost its economy in the direction of technology. But this can be looked in the direction of Agriculture because of its rich lands with nutrients especially in the southern part to support plant and food production. Major foods like cassava, plantain, cocoyam, yam etc and other vegetables needs to be established under an umbrella or a board for sorely implementation, coordination and management to generate money and wealth to boost the Ghanaian economy and feed the world also. The cassava industry in Ghana is serving a greater portion of people and the economy in Ghana and beyond. One of the main loving staple food in Ghana is fufu which is used to serve visitors and people

during and on occasions. Fufu is served with all kinds of soup and is a dish loved by all in Ghana hence an important food in Ghana. Even though this fufu can be prepared with yam, preparation from cassava is at a greater percentage. With this reason in mind, cassava needs assessment, investigation and restoration of the Ghanaian cassava back to its original states like being used in the lives of older generation. Helping restore the cassava back to its original states will help control and manage the resource for now and future generations. The past generations did not do much when it comes to maintenance and protection of natural resources in Ghana for unborn generations. The current technological impact on the international stage is very high with most Ghanaians and Africans unable to see through the reality of things. It is therefore necessary to investigate some of the discrepancies in the cassava production in order to protect its value for the future.

Cassava leaves is also used to serve medicinal purpose in Ghana where various illness or diseases are healed with the cassava plant. Hence it can be said to be a very important plant to the Ghanaian and the world. Even though there is medicinal purpose and benefit from cassava plant, the main focus is on the cassava which is the edible with processing potential into other consumable products like cassava dough, *Agbert (fried cassava dough)*, kokonte, for fufu, for banku etc. Cassava is used to prepare fufu and banku during several occasions like

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during naming ceremony, parties, funerals, weddings, Christmas festivities, Easter, end of engagements (such a learning a trade) and so on. Using cassava is therefore a necessity in Ghana and the requirement and need to research into obtaining good quality edible cassava while protecting and maintaining its identity for future generations. Even though the Ghanaian economy is a middle income economy, it has been sustained from generation past to now. This is because of the abundance and availability of rich lands with good nutrient to support plant growth and production. Cassava therefore thrives and gives good yield seasonally to support usage in the homes, at chop bars, hotels, restaurants, functions (Christmas, Easter and Parties). Better understanding of past events concerning cassava and its production in Ghana is very necessary for better results in this research. With this in mind, there can be assessment, modification, adjustment and refinemenent of cassava into products that will help boost the Ghanaian economy and serve the world at large. Cassava is again massively being used in the Chop bars in Ghana and workers are really doing very well with it. Dining fufu is mostly seen in chop bars where majority of people in Ghana take it as their supper. It is also taken as breakfast in some areas within the country but on a lighter level. This concludes the essence and importance of cassava in the Ghanaian economy.

2. Review of Related Works on Cassava

2.1 The origin of Cassava

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Manihot esculenta commonly called *cassava* is a woody shrub of the spurge family, Euphorbiaceae, native to South America, from Brazil and parts of the Andes (Wikipedia, 2023). Although a perennial plant, cassava is extensively cultivated as an annual crop in tropical and subtropical regions for its edible starchy root tuber, a major source of carbohydrates. Cassava is predominantly consumed in boiled form, but substantial quantities are used to extract cassava starch, called tapioca, which is used for food, animal feed, and industrial purposes. The Brazilian farinha, and the related Gari of West Africa, is an edible coarse flour obtained by grating cassava roots, pressing moisture off the obtained grated pulp, removing all water from the grated pulp and finally drying it (and roasting to obtain the Gari) (Wikipedia, 2023).

Cassava is the third-largest source of food carbohydrates in the tropics, after rice and maize (FAO, 2011; Fauquet et al., 1990; Afedraru, 2019). Cassava is a major staple food in the developing world, providing a basic diet for over half a billion people (FAO, 1995). With this staple food, daily demands for food is met in various dimensions as it's prepared in various ways to meet daily food needs. It is one of the most drought-tolerant crops, capable of growing on marginal soils. Nigeria is the world's largest producer of cassava, while Thailand is the largest exporter of cassava starch (Wikipedia, 2023).

Cassava is classified as either sweet or bitter. Like other roots and tubers, both bitter and sweet varieties of cassava contain antinutritional factors and toxins, with the bitter varieties containing much larger amounts (FAO, 1990). It must

be properly prepared before consumption, as improper preparation of cassava can leave enough residual cyanide to cause acute cyanide intoxication (CPV, 2017; BBC, 2016) goiter, ataxia, partial paralysis, or death (Soto-Blanco et. al., 2010). The more toxic varieties of cassava have been used in some places as famine food during times of food insecurity (CPV, 2017; FAO, 1990). Farmers often prefer the bitter varieties because they deter pests, animals, and thieves (Chiwona-Karlton et. al., 2002) and is the most used for Gari and starch manufacturing. The cassava root is long and tapered, with a firm, homogeneous flesh encased in a detachable rind, about 1 millimetre (1mm) thick, rough and brown on the outside. Commercial cultivars can be 5 to 10 centimeters (2 to 4 in) in diameter at the top, and around 15 to 30 cm (6 to 12 in) long. (Wikipedia, 2023). A woody vascular bundle runs along the root's axis. The flesh can be chalk-white or yellowish. Cassava roots are very rich in starch and contain small amounts of calcium (NNDSTR, 2016) which in a way is important to healthy life living. However, they are poor in protein and other nutrients. In contrast, cassava leaves are a good source of protein for animal and human (Latif et. al., 2015) nutrition, but deficient in the amino acid methionine (Ravindran, 1992). A lot of cassava varieties have been identified in Ghana and this is shown in **Table 1** below.

Cassava Variety	Year Released	Maturity Period (months)	Uses
Afisiafi	1993	12 - 15	Starch, flour, Gari
Abasafitaa	1993	12 - 15	Starch, flour, Gari
Tekbankye	1997	12 - 15	Starch, flour, Gari
Dokuduade	2005	12	Fufu, ampesi, Gari
Agbelifia	2005	12	Starch , Gari
Essam bankye	2005	12	Flour, Gari
Bankyehemaa	2005	9 - 12	Fufu, Flour, Gari
Capevars bankye	2005	9 -12	Fufu, Flour, Fufu, Gari
Bankye botan	2005	12 - 15	Flour, Gari, Starch
Eskamaye	2005	15 - 18	Tuo, Kokonte
Filindiakong	2005	15 - 18	Tuo, Kokonte
Nyerikobga	2005	15 - 18	Tuo, Kokonte
Nkabom	2005	12 - 15	Starch, Fufu
IFAD	2005	12 - 15	Starch, Fufu
Ampong	2010	12	Flour, Starch, Fufu
Broni bankye	2010	12	Flour, bakery Product
Sika bankye	2010	12	Flour, Starch
Otuhia	2010	12	Flour, Starch

(Source: Afrane, 2016)

Table 1: Improved Cassava Varieties and their Characteristics

2.2 Vegetative Reproduction

Asexual propagation or reproduction from vegetative parts of the original plant, is possible because every cell of the plant contains the genetic information necessary to regenerate the entire plant (Tchoundjeu et. al., 2006). With this genetic information, young plants produced from parent plant vegetatively have similar characteristics and features comparable to the parent plant. Reproduction can occur through the formation of adventitious roots and shoots or through the uniting of vegetative parts by grafting or budding. Stem cuttings (in the case of cassava) and layers have the ability to form adventitious roots, and root cuttings can regenerate a new shoot system (Tchoundjeu et. al., 2006). It is also possible for leaves to regenerate both new roots and new shoots while a stem and a root can be grafted together to form a single plant (Tchoundjeu et. al., 2006). Many agroforestry tree species are dioecious and farmers often report that when a tasty or large fruit from a superior fruit tree for example is planted, the seedling does not perform up to their expectations. In most cases they are interested only in the female, fruit-bearing individuals and sometimes retain a few male pollinator trees around (Tchoundjeu et. al., 2006). It is difficult if not impossible to predict in juvenile plants their sex expression. In this context, vegetative propagation of the female trees could help increase the number of fruit bearing trees on farm (Tchoundjeu et. al., 2006). Vegetative reproduction types includes stem, roots, leaves, bulbs, cuttings, grafting, layering and tissue culture. In all these, young ones with the same characteristics are

produced to grow and mature into parents plants with further vegetative propagation making the process cyclical.

2.3 Vegetative reproduction in Cassava's

All of the important fruit-crop plants in the United States, many of the ornamentals, a few crops like potatoes, and some of the nut and forest trees are multiplied or propagated for commercial production by vegetative means (Magness, 1937). This means that a new plant is developed from a vegetative part of a mother plant, such as a cutting, sucker, stem or bud, instead of from a seed, as is the case with most of the cereal, forage, and vegetable crops. This fact is extremely important from the stand point of the principles and methods employed in the improvement of fruit crops by breeding. Under the Microscope, a seed in the ordinary plant develops from a single cell, the fertilized egg which has received in the fertilizing process chromosomes from both the female or seed parent and the male or pollen parent. These chromosomes transmit the hereditary factors or genes from both parents, and the offspring that develops from this cell therefore, inherits the characteristics of both parents (Magness, 1937). If the germ cells from the two parents carry genes that are alike for all characteristics, the plants that develop from the seeds will be very similar to these parents. On the other hand, if the parents transmit unlike genes for various characters, many of the offspring will vary widely from either parent because of the

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effects of dominance, recessiveness, or modifying factors (Magness, 1937).

In vegetative propagation of cassava, the new plant also develops from a single original cell (Stem cutting). Although the bud or other propagative tissue may consist of thousands of cells, at one stage of its development only a single cell is involved. This cell carries the same genes as the mother tissue from which it was developed, and the genetic characteristics of the new tissue in the case of cassava correspond to those of the mother plant (Magness, 1937). From the hereditary standpoint, it may be said that the vegetative offspring of a cassava plant is a part of that plant itself rather than a new individual. The original tree or plant has probably been dead for more than a century (Magness, 1937) but through propagation, new offspring's are generated for continuity of the plants generation. This is probably the essence of vegetative propagation in cassava, crops and plants.

In consideration of cell division in vegetative tissues, the division of a cell to form two daughter cells in vegetative tissue is quite similar to that described in the article on Heredity (Magness, 1937). Each vegetative cell consists of the cell wall, the cytoplasm, and a nucleus. The nucleus, while the cell is in the resting stage—that is, not in the act of dividing—contains numerous chromatin granules, just as the germ cells do. In the beginning stages of cell division these chromatin granules collect in threadlike bodies, which are the forerunners of the

more definitely organized chromosomes (Magness, 1937). These threadlike bodies are usually more or less separate, though in some cases appear to be arranged end to end. Later they break up into independent chromosomes. At this stage one very important step occurs that does not occur in the same way in the germ cell. After the chromosomes are formed in the vegetative cell, each chromosome appears to split longitudinally into two parts giving twice the original number. Each of these parts appears to function as an independent chromosome. After that, the process is like that in the germ cell (Magness, 1937). The two halves of each original chromosome migrate, one to each of two poles on opposite sides of the nucleus. These two groups of chromosomes, one at either pole now reorganize as separate daughter nuclei, each similar to the original one (Magness, 1937). A cell wall is formed between the two daughter nuclei, and there are two complete cells instead of the original one. Each of these cells however, has the same number of chromosomes as the original, whereas if they were germ cells they would have half the original number (Magness, 1937).

2.4 Root system development in cassava plant

Roots are the main storage organs in cassava which grows and develops into a cassava food. In plants propagated from true seeds, a typical primary tap root system is developed similar to dicot species (Alfredo, 2002). The radicle of the germinating seed grows vertically downward and develops into a taproot,

from which adventitious roots originate. Later the taproot and some adventitious roots become storage roots. In plants grown from stem cutting like cassava, the roots are adventitious and they arise from the basal-cut surface of the stake and occasionally from the buds under the soil (Alfredo, 2002). These roots develop to make a fibrous root system. Only a few fibrous roots (between three and ten) start to bulk and become storage roots. Most of the other fibrous roots remain thin and continue to function in water and nutrient absorption. Once a fibrous root become a storage root, its ability to absorb water and nutrients decrease considerably (Alfredo, 2002). The storage roots result from secondary growth of the fibrous roots; thus the soil is penetrated by thin roots, and their enlargement begins only after that penetration has occurred. Anatomically, the cassava root is not a tuberous root, but a true root which cannot be used for vegetative reproduction. The mature cassava storage root has three distinct tissues: bark (periderm), peel (or cortex) and parenchyma (Alfredo, 2002). The perenchyma which is the edible part of the fresh root, comprises of approximately 85% of total weight, consisting of xylem vessels radially distributed in matrix of starch containing cells (Wheatley and Chuzel, 1993). The peel layer which comprises of selerenchyma, cortical parenchyma and phloem, constitutes 11 – 20% of root weight (Barrios and Bressani, 1967). The periderm is a thin layer made of few cells which are very thick and as growth progresses, the outermost part usually slough off. Root size and shape depend on cultivar and

environmental conditions; variability in size within a cultivar is greater than that found in other root crops (Wheatley and Chuzel, 1993).

2.5 Flowering in cassava plants

Cassava is a monoecious species producing both male (pistillate) and female (staminate) flowers on the same plant. The inflorescence is generally formed at the insertion point of the reproductive branching; occasionally inflorescence can be found in the leaf axils on the upper part of the plant. The female flower located on the lower part of the inflorescence, are fewer in number than male flowers which are numerous on the upper part of the inflorescence. Studies have indicated that application of cytokinin via localized spray to the shoot apical region increased the female-to-male ratio while maintaining the number of total flowers in cassava (Tim et. al., 2021). This effect has also been observed in response to foliar spray in other members of Euphorbiaceae including *Jatropha curcas* (Pan and Xu, 2011; Chen et al., 2014; Pan et al., 2014) and *Plukenetia volubilis* (Fu et al., 2014), which are more prolific than cassava in total flower production. The cytokinin Benzyladenine (BA) effect on feminization was not dependent on the co-application of silver thiosulfate (STS) or pruning treatments which increase total flower production (Tim et. al., 2021). The feminizing effect of BA on flower development was dose dependent in *Jatropha curcas* (Chen et al., 2014), in agreement with the present study of cassava with cytokinin

Benzyladenine (BA) as a sole treatment. By increasing the concentration of cytokinin Benzyladenine (BA), the percentage of female flowers increased from about 12% in the untreated control, to about 30% with 0.22 mM cytokinin Benzyladenine (BA), to over 80% with 0.5mM cytokinin Benzyladenine (BA) (Tim et al., 2021). Studies are also in agreement with studies that have shown that cytokinin Benzyladenine (BA) is more effective at producing female flowers when treatments are begun at an early stage in flower development (Fröschle et al., 2017; Luo et al., 2020). In contrast to the effect of cytokinin Benzyladenine (BA) in increasing the proportion of flowers that were female, cytokinin Benzyladenine (BA) had no effect on the total number of flowers and fruits (Tim et al., 2021). This differs from studies in other members of Euphorbiaceae in which cytokinin Benzyladenine (BA) treatments also resulted in an increase in the total number of flowers and fruits (Pan and Xu, 2011; Chen et al., 2014; Fu et al., 2014; Pan et al., 2014). On the other hand, when either STS or pruning was combined with BA, the female-to-male ratio was maintained in a larger population of flowers (Tim et al., 2021). A few studies of Euphorbiaceae-family plants have shown that pruning (Pineda et al., 2020), silver thiosulfate (STS) (Hyde et al., 2020), or cytokinin Benzyladenine (BA) (Fu et al., 2014) affect flower development when applied separately but until the current study, these treatments were not applied together (Tim et al., 2021). Current studies have disclosed that combining these three factors substantially improved reproductive development in

cassava (Tim et al., 2021). While silver thiosulfate (STS) and pruning acted additively to increase the total number of flowers, cytokinin Benzyladenine (BA) increased the female-to-male ratio of flowers. This in turn led to greater fruit development than in each of the factors applied singly (Tim et al., 2021).

2.6 Soil conditions to promote cassava production

The soil components and texture is a major constituents of cassava cultivation. Good soil supports plant growth and is highly imperative for optimum crop production. Determining the appropriate soil that supports cassava growth is key and vital to optimal cassava production in Nigeria (Biratu et al., 2018; Senkoro et al., 2018; Ezui et al., 2016; Janket et al., 2018). Soil quality plays an essential role in cassava cultivation. That is why good farmlands with good soil quality are assets to farmers. Invariably, soil quality has been equated with having a good effect on agricultural productivity (Janket et al., 2018; Antwi et al., 2017; Boansi, 2017). The Cassava crop is one of the few plants that grow in any weather condition to support the growth of cassava. It is drought-resistant and can grow and survive anywhere, even in regions where other crops cannot. The cassava crops are highly adaptable to weather conditions and climate change, yet they cannot tolerate and survive where there is flooding. Cassava plants can tolerate acidity and low soil fertility (Pardales et al., 1999; El-Sijarkawy et al., 1984; Keating et al., 1982) for adaptation and growth. The type of soil cassava is cultivated on determines the level of yields that will

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be obtained. For instance, clay and sandy soils support the growth of the leaves and stem at the expense of the cassava root development and growth. Loamy soil promotes and boosts root development more than the leaves and stems. That is why loamy soil is preferred for optimal cassava yield. This soil type also gives the roots enough space to grow based on the nutrients available in the soil. Soil fertility plays a role in the optimal yield of cassava plants. Salty or swampy soils do not support cassava growth and development (Keating et al., 1979; Daryanto et al., 2016; Keating et al., 1982). Cassava is cultivated annually in Nigeria in latitudes between 30°N and 30°S (Keating et al., 1982). Because cassava is a tropical crop and can survive hot climates, there is no decline in growth in the dry season. During the rainy season, the growth of cassava continues to develop and advance to maturity in a better way comparable to the dry season. The average soil p^H for optimal cassava growth and development oscillates between P^H of 5.5 to 6.5. Soils with a p^H less than 5.5 are acidic and can support cassava growth only if treated with lime. Incorporating lime in the land preparation process helps to normalize the soil p^H before cassava cultivation. This is a common practice here in Nigeria. The growth of cassava can be affected if there is a high salt concentration in the soil with a p^H as high as 7.8 (Ezui et al., 2016). In warm weather conditions, it may take cassava plants up to 8 months to produce cassava tubers for harvesting. During extreme weather conditions like the dry or cold season, producing cassava tubers may take 18 or more months. That is, cassava plants begin to experience a decline in growth if the soil temperature falls below 10 °C (50 °F) (Keating et al., 1982). The

cassava crop grows well in areas that are humid and moist. Low temperature causes slow growth and reduced yields. The common climate condition for cassava plants to grow well is in humid-warm weather at a temperature of 25-29 °C (77-84 °F) and the soil temperature at 30 °C (86 °F). Arable farmlands grow cassava better all year round. The growth of cassava can only take place in regions or areas that are frost free (Biratu et al., 2018; Senkoro et al., 2018).

2.7 Rainfall pattern in Ghana and impacts on cassava production

Understanding the decadal and/or annual variability and distributions of rainfall of a region is important and useful especially for agricultural activities (Logah et al., 2013). In this case, production of cassava either for commercial or family use is highly rainfall dependent. Studies shows variation on high and low rainfall distributions in Ghana. With respect to previous studies, results showed a general decline in mean annual rainfall for the period 1981-2010 with high rainfalls shifting to the South-western corner of the country. It could be deduced that mean decadal rainfall amounts in Ghana is on a gradual increase from 1981 to 2010, though the rate at which it is increasing is on a decline, i.e. from 8.6 % in 1991-2000 to 2.6 % in 2001-2010 (Logah et al., 2013). Water makes up 70% of the earth surface dependent on by both plants and animals for survival and existence. It is an important component in everyday life, from basic domestic use to national and global development (UNWWD, 2006). The use of rain water over the years has gained its importance as a valuable alternative or

supplementary water resource. Rain water can be used for multiple purposes ranging from domestic and industrial water supply, sanitation and disease prevention and rainfed agriculture (Logah et al., 2013). It is thus evident that water forms an integral part of the development of human societies and food production. The most critical factor that sustains cassava crop productivity in rainfed agriculture is the availability of water. In Ghana, agricultural production serves as the main economic sector, employing about 56 % of the workforce and accounting for about 28% of gross domestic product (GDP) (CIA, 2012). However this sector depends heavily on rainfall. It is therefore imperative to say that cassava production to generate high yields is highly rainfall dependent in Ghana. Variability of rainfall from season to season greatly affects soil water availability to crops such as cassava, and thus risks crop productivity. Most studies conducted in Ghana on rainfall variability and distributions were limited to selected regions or stations (Adiku et al., 1997; Gyau-Boakye et al., 2000; Logah et al., 2013). Results from studies shows the risk of a dry spell during the dry season to be higher in the north of the country than in the south. Reference (Adiku et al., 1997) also observed similar trends in the intra-seasonal rainfall variability of Accra in the south and Tamale in the north. (Anang et al., 1977) reported the variability and distribution of mean annual rainfall totals in Ghana, with mean rainfall values between 1,000-1,400 mm covering more than 50 % of the entire country. Higher mean annual rainfall amount exceeding 1,900 mm occurs in parts of Ashanti and Western Regions of Ghana (Logah et al., 2013). Recent climate trends show highly variable inter-

annual and inter-decadal rainfall amounts in Ghana. Various models predicted that rainfall will continue to decrease in all the agro-ecological zones and river basins of Ghana (WRC, 2010; McSweeney, 2012; Kankam-Yeboah, 2013; Obuobie et al., 2012; Logah et al., 2012) whilst other models also predicted increases in the mean annual rainfall averaged over the entire country (McSweeney, 2012) to increase crop production. This makes it very difficult to identify and/or predict with certainty the long term trends of rainfall in the country and resultant impacts on cassava production. Knowing the pattern of rainfall in a region is thus indispensable due to its usefulness in guiding water users, especially food producers in their planning and decision making (Logah et al., 2013). Studies therefore have sought to analyze the variability of mean annual rainfall in Ghana to support decision-making, planning and designing in the fields of hydrology and agriculture for better results when it comes to cassava production in Ghana.

3 Study Area and Employed methodology

3.1 Study Area for the Research

The study area for this research work is within Nsutam in the Eastern Region of Ghana. The community which is within the Fanteakwa South district has a population of about 7000 (2021 population census). Nsutam community which is a farming community with petty tradings among the indigenous is now a gold mining community. Several gold mines have been discovered with gold mining operations going on 24/7. As a farming community, its rich lands supports crop production

such as cassava, maize, cocoyam, yam, plantain etc. serving as daily source of bread and income for the indigenous. Cocoa and coconut which are international resources are also produced by the communities' rich lands. Vegetables including cabbage, pepper, garden eggs, ginger etc are also obtained from the communities rich lands to support lives. The farm product under study is a major crop planted and used in the community but at a lower rate. Farmers do not produce cassava on large scale but mainly for their homes and some sold at an infinitesimal rate for serving butter trade purposes. The rich lands of Nsutam supports cassava production yielding at high rate all year round. The only problem is how good, quality and sweet the cassava is to support human existence. Depicted in **Fig. 1** is the map of the study area for this research work. It gives the exact location of Nsutam community within the Fanteakwa south district of the Eastern Region of Ghana. The discovery of gold within the community has increased migrations from all over the country Ghana and beyond to boost the communities' economy and way of life. This has made the community lively than former and increasing gold production from Ghana to the international world.

Fig 1: Nsutam community within Fanteakwa South District

3.2 Methodology employed for the Research

Research works involves coming out with a procedure or steps to access information and establish findings. The method employed for this work is the Stationed Assessment and

Evaluation Model (SAAEM). This model involves farm visits to access fully matured cassava plants, analyze the various stages involved in the growth of the cassava plant. Procedural research work includes assessment and analysis of roots formation, leaves formation, access to all conditions necessary for photosynthesis, flowering, maturity and cassava food formation. Vegetative reproduction of the cassava plant is done by taking a stem from the cassava plant and planting or incorporating into the soil to monitor and analyze adventitious roots formation, leaves formation and other process.

4 Research Findings and discussions

4.1 Soil characterization and impacts on cassava production at Nsutam

The Ghanaian and Nsutam community lands are rich in nutrients and support various crop production to boost the Ghanaian economy and address the problem of food insecurity. Even though the people of Ghana do complain of food scarcity, one can easily boast of getting access to all kinds of food items on the market to support daily life. This is a clear indication that the various lands especially in the southern part of Ghana is supporting crop (e.g. cassava) production. The rich loamy soils in the southern part of Ghana which receives two rainfall seasons within the year is supporting crop and vegetables production. It's only in the northern part of Ghana that one find lands degraded of rich soil nutrients to support crop

production. This is because of the one seasonal rainfall experience each year. Even that, farmers develop various strategies like composting to obtain fine textured loamy compost to be applied on lands. Correct application of such compost on the farms result in high yield of farm produce such as millet, maize, rice, vegetables etc. Soils found in the study area includes loamy soil, sandy, clay. With these various soils, correct estimation of good soil for cassava or crop production results in a high yield for a particular soil.

Because of the good nature of the soils in the southern part of Ghana and in the study area, cassava production is the most benefited. Cassava plant can be there for long once it is matured and can be in the soil for years. The impact of good soil with good characteristics on cassava production is positive. This is because high yields are harvested each year to meet the various purposes derived from cassava. This includes for fufu, Gari, kokonte, starch, alcoholic drinks and for biofuel.

4.2 Changes in cassava good quality and sweetness due to changes in season

The good quality and sweetness level of Ghanaian cassava has changed drastically and no more eatable by a lot of Ghanaians. This is not the case when compared to ages past such as in the 1980s and 1990s. In years past, cassava was a delicious food enjoyed by the old and young men and women. There is about 93% loss in value and no or low level of interest in the cassava

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hence no more eatable or enjoyable. This same cooked cassava in years past was served with delicious stews which was likened and enjoyed by all. This is not same today as current generation frown on eating cassava and thinks is a meal associated with the poor. Cooked cassava is comparable to cooked yam which were eatable in ages past. But the shift is now about 94% in the direction of cooked yam and is even used as a substitute for cassava when dealing with fufu. All this reasons boils to the fact that cassava has lost its good quality and sweetness after cooking. Research findings established that, a usable cassava during a period within the season becomes unusable for some short period before becoming usable (for fufu or eatable) again. This is usually the case when there is a shift from dry season to rainy season and vice versa.

During such periods, farmers and restaurant operators usually have problems with cooked cassava's hence running at a lost in most times. For instance, 100% uncooked cassava will give you 100% bad cassava's after cooking if not obtained in its right state. The current cassava in the southern part of Ghana is the bitter type hence does not support direct eating of the cassava after cooking. In times past, edible cassava was very sweet and enjoyable by all. This made the old and young to like eating the cassava with stew which even comes with flavors. There seems to be a change in the cassava in Ghana and hence a rejection by most in eaten and enjoying cassava. This has increased and generated much pressure on the use of yam in Ghana. This has

increased prices of yam in Ghana mostly in the Eastern Region of Ghana. Citizens are now complaining of the economy hence the need to work on cassava status to buttress yam usage within the region.

4.3 Impacts of cassava production on Nsutam community and Ghanaian economy

The impact of cassava production on Nsutam community is in the positive direction but not to a high degree where it generates income for the people. The only most appropriate way in which indigenous of Nsutam are benefiting is in direction of food production and consumption. In this case, cassava food is processed into various products to meet daily needs and advance in life. Some of the food items obtained after processing the cassava is for fufu, for Gari, for starch, as cassava dough to serve as addictive in the preparation of banku. It is also processed into *Akbet* after frying. The cassava produced in this community is usually obtained from the market either within the community or from outside the community. In both cases, the cassava is bought at the market at a value to meet this demand. The situation of either the cassava being in a good or bad state still persist as cassava in the Eastern Region has issues of not being having eatable characteristics. The issue of commercial farming of some farm products is a problem in the Eastern Region of Ghana comparable to other regions like Ahafo, Western Region, Volta Region etc. This is one of the problems that needs to be addressed in the Eastern Region of

Ghana where there will be the establishment of commercial farms where some of these farm products (crops) will be planted to feed mother Ghana and the world. It will even serve as an opportunity to employ graduates and shift graduates attention from white color jobs to commercial farming (Green color job – Greenish nature of plants and what can be obtained from plants and farming) to help mankind and the world. The president, Nana Akuffo Addo Dankwa government started the ‘planting for food and job’ policy which is in force but current state of affairs on the market, the price of food and the quantity that can be obtained on the market makes the policy questionable. It therefore boils down to future leaders and graduates to reframe the policy into ‘planting for food and money’ policy where farming will be done on commercial scale or dimension to produce farm products on large scale or mass production of farm products. When this done, Ghana will have a lot of food on the local market and the price of food will fall drastically to boost the economy and put a smile on the face of the poor citizen. Some of these same farm products will boost the export industry where a lot of the crops produced will be sold to the international world. In such cases, countries without a particular crop or unable to produce such crops will buy from Ghana to promote the culture of Ghana (in terms of eatable farm produce) while boosting the economic standard of Ghana. In such a situations, it will be justifiable to say that *Green color jobs* have been created for the unemployed graduate or citizen as there is generation and production of food and money from

the greenish nature of plants. This will give a clear fulfilment of president’s policy as there is planting for food and money. That is, as cassava food and other crops is produced and obtained from green plants to feed the unemployed graduate, the rich and poor citizen, money is generated from export from the selling of these food items to the world. This generates money worth Billions of Pound Sterling, cedis or dollars into government pocket and finally into the pockets and hands of citizens to live a meaningful life.

4.4 Mass production of cassava and associated uses

To the Ghanaian economy, cassava is a very important crop especially to the people living in the south. The fufu obtained from cassava is a very eatable and appreciated food by the people in the south hence the need for cassava. This food is much of importance and promoting Ghanaian culture hence the need to work on the source as its preparation is from the mixture of cassava and plantain or cassava and cocoyam. It hence deem fit to produce this cassava on large scale or mass production of the crop to feed the Ghanaian economy and serve the world. Because of its localized way of preparation, modern technology has resulted in obtaining cassava flour which is used to serve many purposes both locally and internationally. Cassava has imbedded in it important nutrients that promotes digestive health and maintains insulin sensitivity in the body. Cassava flour is used in baking bread, cookies, cakes, for thickening sauce etc. Cassava is also used for making

biofuel, preparation of alcoholic beverages, preparation of ethanol (alcohol). For instance, Kasiri (cassava beer) is an alcoholic drink made from cassava by Amerindians in Suriname and Guyana. With this few uses in mind, one can attest the various uses and products obtainable from cassava for the benefit of mankind. It is therefore necessary that cassava be produced by Ghanaians on large scale or on mass production for processing into some of these usable products. This will boost the Ghanaian economy and increase export of cassava onto the international market for the benefit of other nations and the world. It will increase Ghana's revenue obtained from export products and serve as another natural resources comparable to cocoa or coffee in Ghana. In order to achieve this in Ghana, it is very necessary to establish the cassava industry on its own comparable to other institutions like those obtained from cocoa and oil palm. It will be justified to have an institution like Cassava Research Institute of Ghana (CARIG) comparable to Cocoa Research Institute of Ghana or Oil palm Research Institute of Ghana. Other major crops will comparably be done same for by producing them on large scale after establishing them under a body of institution. For instance; PRIG for Plantain Research Institute of Ghana, (CORIG) for Cocoyam Research Institute of Ghana, (CCRIG) for Coconut Research Institute of Ghana, (YYRIG) for Yellow Yam Research Institute of Ghana, (CIRIG) for Cotton Industrialization Research Institute of Ghana and same for vegetables like cabbage, pepper, tomatoes and so on. Once this is done, big institutions

formed from cassava, plantain, yellow yam, cocoyam, coconut, pepper, cabbage, tomatoes etc will be obtained with different sub – branches undergoing different assignments to obtain different products – for biofuel, for alcohol and alcoholic beverages, bread making, for fufu, for Gari, for Eba (in Nigeria) etc; in the case of cassava and same for all the other crops and vegetables. Cassava is a fine natural resources that is being exploited in the right direction by other countries for the benefit of mankind but under exploited in Ghana. Ghana has rich lands that is supporting the production of cassava on large scale but on a lighter note. Hence very necessary for the mass production of cassava for processing and refinement into some of the listed products stated above for the benefit of the poor Ghanaian citizen and the world. While achieving the stated purposes above, unemployment problem will be addressed in Ghana as graduates continue to complain of jobs in the country. This can be done same for the production of cocoyam, yellow yam, plantain, coconut and water yam on large scale in Ghana comparable to that of cassava as discussed above.

4.5 Rainfall pattern adaptability and impacts on cassava production in Ghana

The rainfall pattern and regime in Ghana is a good one from divine creation comparable to other countries. The southern part of Ghana has two rainfall periods while the northern part experiences rainfall during the June – July rains throughout the year. During such periods, precipitation of different amounts

and duration are obtained to enrich the soil for crop production resulting in different yields for the benefit of mankind. Because of this, lands in the southern part of Ghana are rich lands due to the continues rainfall resulting in continues decomposition of plants and farming residues. This is same in the northern part during the rainfall seasons where farming by farmers is at its peak. Compost preparation is seen as a saving tool used by farmers in the northern part of Ghana to prepare and improve the degradable lands to support crop production. This is done together with irrigation during the dry season to support crop production and plant growth as stated by Danquah (2023) on composting to improve degradable lands. This is what has been used over decades and still in use today to boost life in the north. Most of the dry season farming is done close to water bodies like the White Volta (WV) in Upper East Region of Ghana. During such periods vegetables like okro, tomatoes, pepper, water melons, onions etc are produced in different amounts. It is therefore justifiable to say that, crop production is even done during the long spell drought in the northern part of Ghana. The good rainfall pattern has therefore generated lands rich in nutrients that is supporting cassava production in Ghana and the resultant yields obtained yearly. Producing cassava on large scale or mass production of cassava in Ghana to serve the Ghanaian economy and the world is therefore not a problem because of the good rainfall pattern in Ghana.

4.6 Functionality of 2020's cassava comparable to 1980's and 1900's cassava in Ghana

Cassava in Ghana has been in existence over centuries and used by the citizens to meet daily food demands in achieving Sustainable Development Goals 2 (SDG 2). During that period, cassava is seen as sweet eatable food very delicious and enjoyable by both young and old. This is still in place and at work in other parts of the world but not in Eastern Region of Ghana and at the study area. The sweet soft eatable cassava variety is very rare to find in the study area and in the Eastern Region of Ghana. The only thing one can boast about is its processing into products like fufu, Gari, cassava dough, starch etc (**Table 1**). This shouldn't be the case since cassava is comparable to all the kinds of yams and carbohydrates food enjoyed by Ghanaians. Both cassava and yams give carbohydrates and can be processed into fufu and other consumable products hence justified as same. But current generations of Ghanaians frown on eating cassava as compared to yams. Field investigation indicated that the sweet eatable variety called '*Tekbankye*' (**Table 1**) truly existed but in minute quantity and can be found in some communities. In the 1990s, this very variety existed in large amounts but the introduction of new varieties from Mampong into Fantekwa constituency and Eastern Region for projects and research works resulted in the extinction of the sticks (*Tekbankye*) from the Region. This research works and introduction of new varieties and their

sticks into the region and Fantekwa constituency has given rise to cassava tubers no more eatable, nonfunctional during seasonal changes (dry season to rainy season) and other complications posing problems as one tries to address SDG 2. It is therefore recommended that, researchers, Ministry of Food and Agriculture in Ghana and workers of MOFA start working on how to identify a source of the 'Tekbankye' variety (in addition to Nkankama) as it is the eatable variety and used for food. Once identified, worked on for multiplication of the sticks and distributed to farmers as it has the potential of serving the same purpose of yams in Ghana and even unto the international world to help poor countries. In addition to farmer's contribution to produce more cassava tubers from the Tekbankye variety, there can be commercial farming. This will be initiated and implemented by Government of Ghana (GoG) and Ministry of Food and Agriculture (MOFA) to produce more sticks and cassava tubers to boost the economy and exported to generate income for GoG.

5 CONCLUSION

Cassava tubers production on small or large scale is dependent on vegetative reproduction. Stem cutting enhances one parent stick of cassava to be multiplied and generating a number of parent plants. This is obtained after planting the small stick, going through root development, sprouting of leaves, soil enrichment through rainfall and if possible addition of fertilizers and flowering unto maturity. With this in mind, a

number of cassava varieties exist in Ghana. This includes Afisiafi, Abasafitaa, Tekbankye, Essam bankye, Agbelifia etc with its associated uses as seen in **Table 1**. The one most sort after in this research and investigation is the *Tekbankye* with the uses of for ampesi (eatable), fufu and Gari. The research work looks at how it is soft, good, sweet and eatable and was consumed in the 1980s and 1990s. This variety is rare and no more eatable and enjoyable by Ghanaians which is comparable to yam and considered as carbohydrates foods. Research findings indicated that the Tekbankye is found in only one community (Nkankama) and in minute quantity. It is hence justifiable for mass production of this Tekbankye in large quantity to be added to eatable foods like yam, plantain, cocoyam etc. This will help to boost the Ghanaian economy (as SDG 2) is addressed and generate revenue through export to the international market for the development of Ghana. Mass production of cassava and establishment of cassava under one body named CARIG will help boost cassava crop production and associated functionalities. This can be done same for other crops like plantain, coconut, yam, cocoyam to help boost the Ghanaian economy and feed the world at large.

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